

Role of Code of Conduct in Promoting Good Governance with Specific Reference to Mopani District Municipality

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The Mopani District Municipality (MDM) in Limpopo Province, South Africa, has faced persistent challenges in achieving clean audit outcomes and effective service delivery. To address these governance issues, municipal officials must conduct themselves ethically in performing their daily duties. They must take cognisance that professional ethics in public administration are vital to ensure moral effective service delivery. This manuscript is based on the study which aimed to critically examine how the implementation and enforcement of the code of conduct influence governance practices within the MDM. The study used a mixed-method approach. In the study, interviewed respondents were (10), and questionnaires were distributed to the respondents (190). The total number of respondents was 200. The study has revealed that MDM has not effectively implemented or enforced the code of conduct. The lack of adherence to the code's principles, such as treating people with respect and courtesy and complying with applicable laws, has undermined its potential to promote good governance.

Keywords: Code of conduct, local government, governance, good governance, values, service delivery

Recent scandals involving municipal officials and their unethical behavior have captured the attention of governments globally. As noted by Manyaka and Sebola (2013:76) the unethical actions of municipal officials have sparked a widespread international dialogue on good governance, emphasizing the need for governments to adopt a more proactive stance in combating corruption. Officials in the Mopani district municipality bear the responsibility of being accountable to their citizens; thus, they are anticipated to execute their responsibilities with competence, courtesy, and integrity, while avoiding unethical behavior that undermines the moral fabric of society. In order to promote ethical conduct within local government, the South African government has implemented several legislative measures, including the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996, the Local Government: Municipal Systems Act, 2000 (Act 32 of 2000), and the Batho-Pele White Paper of 1997. Unfortunately, South African society has not been immune to this moral decline. The concept of a code of conduct appears to be experiencing a resurgence, albeit amidst considerable controversy and speculation. There is a palpable concern that the global community is increasingly neglecting the significance of ethical considerations. This code aims to educate

stakeholders about the expected behaviours and to provide guidelines for decision-making and interactions with constituents.

Mle and Maclean (2011:1366) emphasize that when a government identifies a necessity for a service to be provided to its citizens, it establishes a department or institution to deliver such a service. This includes the provision of housing, the supply of water and electricity, sanitation, and any other services that may be required by the populace. Consequently, the overarching aim or objective of any government is the welfare of the community's residents. It is imperative for every government to enhance the welfare of its citizens (De Bruijn & Dicke, 2006:79). Negative audit opinions regarding municipalities serve as evidence of a lack of good governance, professionalism, ethics, and integrity (Kondlo & Maserumule, 2010:77). Notwithstanding these observations, the local government in South Africa is marked by numerous allegations of unethical behavior, raising significant concerns regarding the effective delivery of services to the public. One stipulation in the Mopani District Municipality's code of conduct for employees is that municipal staff members must consistently act in the best interests of the municipality, ensuring that the credibility and integrity of the municipality remain intact (Mopani District Municipal code of conduct for employees, 2017:2).

Municipal officials have faced challenges in maintaining ethical conduct and showcasing honesty and integrity within the framework of the minimum standards established and codified by various international human rights and good governance conventions. Although ethical leadership and governance represent a global concern, this issue is more pronounced in developing nations compared to developed countries for several reasons. These reasons may encompass, but are not limited to, cultural relativity, the contextual differences among various governments, and the duration of mobilization and investment in the doctrine of human rights worldwide. Tintswalo, Mazenda, Masiya, and Shava (2022:307) contend that ethics has emerged as a complex subject across numerous disciplines, including Philosophy, Law, Public Administration, and Politics, as its relevance is contingent upon the specific context in which it is applied. The discussion will also focus on the principles of good governance within local government; the significance of good governance; the origins of the code of conduct;

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the advancements of the code of conduct in the Mopani district municipality; and the influence of a code of conduct on local governance. Ultimately, the manuscript addresses how the local government in South Africa can foster good governance.

Significance of the Study

The importance of this research is rooted in its ability to improve the code of conduct aimed at fostering good governance within the municipalities of the Mopani District Municipality (MDM) by pinpointing the essential principles that ought to be embraced. Additionally, this research will significantly enrich the current body of literature by providing guidance to municipalities on the principles that can be utilized to promote good governance. The Mopani District Municipality has encountered ongoing difficulties concerning ethical leadership and accountability. A study conducted by Mbedzi (2023:8) highlights the vital function that a well-executed Code of Conduct serves in steering municipal officials towards ethical conduct, thus enhancing accountability and integrity within the municipality. MDM has repeatedly faced unfavorable audit results, with concerns such as ineffective political leadership and inadequate internal audit systems being underscored. Rangwato et al. (2024:9) recognize these elements as major factors contributing to the municipality's financial mismanagement. The establishment of a strong Code of Conduct can mitigate these challenges by instituting clear ethical standards and accountability frameworks. Public confidence in local governance is crucial for effective administration. The MDM's Code of Conduct (2025-2026) delineates the expected standards of behavior for officials, with the objective of improving transparency and nurturing public trust in municipal activities (MDM, 2024:5).

Ethical Theoretical Framework: Theory of Deontology

According to Mackinnon (2012:9), the theory provides for ethical principles that encapsulate specific values, which can guide decisions regarding the actions that may be selected and executed in a given situation. Ethical theories and principles represent the shared objectives that each theory aims to fulfill in order to achieve success. Municipal officials require a systematic method for contemplating the ethical implications of their decisions, as well as a framework and terminology for evaluating alternatives from a moral standpoint. Numerous ethical theories are associated with the code of conduct; this study concentrates on the deontological theory due to its relevance. The deontological perspective asserts that the morality of an action is based on rules or principles that govern actions and decisions. A code of conduct generally delineates the ethical obligations and responsibilities anticipated from municipal officials and employees. Maile (2022:44) posits that deontology enables individuals to operate on a broader scale compared to more stringent theories, such as consequentialism. Deontological ethics underscores that individuals should act in accordance with established moral principles, including honesty, fairness, transparency, and respect for the law, simply because it is the morally correct action, rather than for personal benefit or political gain. Within this ethical framework, the morality of an action is determined by the principle, rule, or obligation that governs it, rather than by the outcomes of the action (Mishra & Singh, 2018:7).

In this context, deontology fortifies the ethical basis of

governance practices by encouraging duty-oriented behaviour among municipal leaders. As noted by Spahn (2020,1) Kantian deontology emphasizes autonomy while dismissing human rights. Good governance relies on principles such as accountability, integrity, transparency, and adherence to the rule of law, all of which are robustly endorsed by deontological ethics. When municipal leaders operate from a standpoint of moral obligation, it is more likely that citizens will trust the administration, engage actively in civic activities, and adhere to municipal regulations. This results in increased public trust, diminished corruption, and enhanced efficiency in service delivery, which are essential components of effective governance. Regoli (2019:2) asserts that the advantages of deontological ethics lie in its provision of a framework for human conduct and the establishment of personal responsibility levels. Roby (2018:17) points out that a key benefit of deontology is its capacity to clarify why certain individuals possess the moral authority to hold others accountable for neglecting their responsibilities.

Thus, it can be concluded that within the changing landscape of South Africa, municipal officials are expected to embrace deontological principles, thereby demonstrating a greater awareness of the outcomes associated with public service transformation and service delivery. Maile (2022:45) argues that in order to execute public service and enhance the efficient and cost-effective provision of services in South Africa, it is essential for public officials to implement deontological principles. Nevertheless, a significant challenge arises from the fact that a strict adherence to deontological ethics may overlook the intricate situational realities encountered by municipal officials. For instance, adhering rigidly to a rule without taking into account the wider community needs could result in outcomes that, while technically ethical, are practically problematic. Consequently, although deontology offers a robust moral framework, municipal governance frequently necessitates a balance between duty-based ethics and certain aspects of consequentialism (which involves considering the outcomes).

In the realm of codes of conduct and effective governance, municipal officials are expected to fulfill their responsibilities and obligations when confronted with an ethical dilemma. A municipal official who adheres to deontological theory will arrive at consistent decisions, as these will be grounded in the duties of the individual. According to Kant, the moral worth of an action is determined by the intention behind it, rather than the consequences or results of that action (Iwuagwu 2019:4). The deontological theory holds significant relevance for municipal codes of conduct. Public officials possess moral obligations to engage in actions that are deemed right and to refrain from actions that are considered wrong (Kwemarira, Ntamu, Nsereko, & Balunywa, 2023:1461). This theory fosters a sense of moral responsibility among officials, strengthens the ethical principles that support good governance, and encourages equitable and just treatment of citizens. When municipal leaders embrace and commit to duty-oriented ethical standards, municipalities are more likely to attain governance that is sustainable, accountable, and centered on the needs of the people.

Context of the Problem

Municipal officials fail to provide effective and efficient services to community members as mandated by the Local Government Municipal Systems Act, 2000 (Act 32 of 2000). This failure is attributed to a lack of commitment and insufficient skills among

municipal officials. Consequently, they exhibit indifference towards basic service delivery, as they do not grasp the significance of fulfilling their public responsibilities (Mafunisa, 1999:15). As previously noted, municipal officials often engage in unethical behavior and corruption, which is particularly evident in Limpopo Province. This includes, but is not limited to, asset theft, fund mismanagement, improper tender awards, maladministration, illegal occupation of RDP houses, unjust dismissals, and failure to comply with service delivery standards. Mbandlwa, Dorasamy, and Fagbadebo (2020:249) further emphasize that ethical conduct is crucial not only for politically appointed public officials but also remains a fundamental element for effective public service delivery. Numerous municipalities across South Africa have faced challenges stemming from inadequate service delivery (Ndebele & Lavhelani, 2017:1). Naidoo (2011:655) contends that since the establishment of the new democratic framework in South Africa, the government has implemented various legislative and anti-corruption measures. Nevertheless, despite the existence of numerous legislative and anti-corruption policies, public institutions in South Africa continue to grapple with unethical behavior among their municipal officials. Malan and Smit (2001:15) assert that persistent maladministration and corruption lead to the misappropriation of resources, which adversely impacts the socio-economic development agenda of Limpopo Province.

Section 26 (1) of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 guarantees that all South Africans have the right to access adequate housing. Mafunisa (2007:261) points out various unethical practices occurring in the Limpopo Province. As a developing nation, South Africa is not anticipated to have fully mastered and implemented all aspects of codes of conduct and good governance as seen in developed countries. Nevertheless, there exists significant potential for enhancing the code of conduct and good governance in South Africa, drawing from the historical, contemporary, and future experiences of municipal officials in service delivery (Matshabaphala, 2022:710). Masegare and Ngoepe (2018:584) assert that without robust corporate governance frameworks, municipalities will struggle to identify and manage the essential elements of governance. Ultimately, this study seeks to investigate the function of codes of conduct in fostering good governance and to propose recommendations that could enhance service delivery within local government.

Principles of Good Governance

There are many principles of governance that are discussed in the succeeding section: participation, consensus-oriented and rule of law.

Method

Participants

Matshabaphala (2017:295) posits that it is primarily the traditional closed leadership structures that occasionally infiltrate our daily administration, leading to a repugnant form of governance characterized by dictatorial tendencies and a lack of citizen involvement in decision-making. For effective decision-making, the government must consistently engage with its stakeholders, including residents, civil society, and political parties. Good governance entails that boards recognize their composition and prioritize equity and diversity, both in their structure and hiring

practices. Boards are uniquely positioned to foster diversity within the organization, which is crucial for the health and success of a board, as it benefits from a range of perspectives. Engaging individuals in decision-making processes and the approach to induction is essential. Section 152 of the 1996 Constitution mandates that municipalities in South Africa collaborate with local communities and community-based organizations in all their initiatives and programs. Public participation is a vital process for legitimizing government decisions and addressing the community's needs. It ensures accountability and transparency, which are fundamental to good governance. The involvement of citizens in governance processes is a defining feature of good governance. Public participation is a critical necessity to support the legality of government actions (Jarbandhan, 2021:27). Participation is a crucial step in mobilizing individuals to engage in the decision-making process. It can take direct or indirect forms, but it must be informed and organized. The fulfillment of political rights' aims and objectives hinges on increased public participation in society. The legal framework embodies the rule of law, which guarantees impartiality in the participation process of governance decision-making.

Consensus-Oriented

An enthusiastic, inclusive, and well-informed debate can yield the most profound solutions as participants collaborate to identify common ground among differing perspectives. Effective governance guarantees that resolutions emerge from these dialogues rather than from discord. As previously indicated, whether you serve as a designated facilitator or an engaged participant, grasping this influential framework will enable you to enhance your group's success by achieving optimal participation and efficiency, a more transparent decision-making process, and superior decisions. Decision-making that prioritizes consensus under effective governance implies that the board takes into account the diverse opinions expressed prior to reaching its conclusion, including the requirements of various groups and aspects of the organization that are relevant to the issue at hand. Boards should strive to arrive at a decision that reflects broad consensus, which will benefit both the organization and its community. Governance relies on the collective agreement of individuals within society to be effective. It has the potential to address the interests of both individuals and the community. For effective governance, it is essential to mediate among these various stakeholder interests in instances of conflict. It is the duty of the government to facilitate consensus-oriented decision-making (Ali, 2015:72). From the aforementioned statement, to achieve a wide consensus on what serves the best interests of the group and, where feasible, on policies and procedures, the interests of the populace must be acknowledged.

Rule of Law

Section 217 of the 1996 Constitution establishes provisions for equity, indicating that individuals who have faced prior disadvantages should receive greater preference. The rule of law serves as a crucial component of governance, emphasizing the safeguarding of individual and collective rights in a fair manner. It promotes the establishment of an independent judiciary, which ensures equity, fairness, and justice within society. Effective governance necessitates the existence of just legal frameworks that are applied without bias. The rule of law includes clearly defined

rights and responsibilities, along with mechanisms for their enforcement and the resolution of disputes in an unbiased manner (Jarbandhan, 2021:27). Furthermore, it mandates comprehensive protection of human rights, especially those of minority groups. The unbiased application of laws relies on an independent judiciary and a police force that is both impartial and free from corruption. Another vital aspect of good governance is the rule of law, which requires a just legal framework to be established within society. The rule of law guarantees impartiality, which is essential for the protection of human rights, particularly for the most vulnerable members of society. The independent judiciary, its impartial characteristics, and a police force that is incorruptible are fundamental elements in ensuring the rule of law. Section 9 (1) of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996, which is included in the Bill of Rights, actualizes the principle of the rule of law by highlighting equality before the law. It stipulates that all individuals are equal before the law and entitled to equal protection and benefits under the law, irrespective of their status or background. This section reinforces the notion that no individual is above the law and that the law must be enforced fairly and without discrimination, which is a core principle of the rule of law. Boards must ensure that they act in an ethical and equitable manner, both in their external collaborations and in their decision-making processes.

Why is Good Governance Important

According to Ali (2015:73), effective governance is not merely about making the right choices, but rather about establishing the most effective procedures for arriving at those choices. This implies that good governance should prioritize the creation of a supportive political environment conducive to social and economic progress. Furthermore, good governance has ensured that state resources are directed towards the enhancement of human and productive sectors rather than towards non-human and unproductive areas. Consequently, governance in any society seeks to promote transparency through the exercise of economic, political, and administrative authority. Good governance empowers organizations to create a sustainable and improved future for everyone. It is the responsibility of managers to maintain a focus on overarching strategic objectives while addressing daily operational challenges and fulfilling their obligations, thus it is essential for them to operate with specific governance principles in mind. Good governance pertains to the methodologies for decision-making and implementation. It is not solely about making the right decisions, but rather about the most effective processes for making those decisions. In this regard, the exploration of good governance has gained significant importance within the realms of political science, public administration, and development studies.

Effective governance is crucial for a multitude of advantages. Initially, the caliber of governance must be assessed based on the performance of the pertinent institution. Consequently, the institution's objectives should be explicitly articulated as a primary concern. Subsequently, progressing towards these objectives necessitates the delineation of decision-making rights and processes, alongside the establishment of a feedback mechanism to monitor and regulate performance. Governance pertains to the manner in which an institution is administered; it encompasses the authority, accountability, and controls that are essential within the institution. Governance holds significance for humanity in terms of enhancing quality of life presently and ensuring sustainability for the future.

Good governance advocates for a departure from inefficiency, mismanagement, bureaucratic obstacles, opacity, and corruption (Klimach, Dawidowicz, & Żróbek, 2018:547). It is a fundamental requirement for human development, and governance that promotes human development is characterized as human governance. It is now widely recognized that the primary causes of human deprivation extend beyond mere economic factors. Social and political elements, deeply entrenched in inadequate governance, also play a significant role. Therefore, it is evident that the discourse surrounding good governance emphasizes the inextricable connections between socio-economic and political advancement. As noted by Bolgherini and Lippi (2022:14) numerous vital services are delivered by local governments, with local ward councillors being the elected officials most closely connected to the communities. The South African government has unequivocally stated that local governments and councillors must remain vigilant to community concerns and responsive to local challenges.

Principles of Codes of Conduct

The following are the sources of code of conduct in the municipalities: integrity and transparency, professionalism, accountability, and effectiveness and efficiency.

Integrity and Transparency

The integrity of an organization consists of a framework encompassing a diverse array of elements. These elements are bolstered by a robust internal control program, which includes established standards of conduct (Nyawo, 2017:64). Municipal officials must refrain from placing themselves under any financial or other obligations to external individuals or organizations that may attempt to influence them in the execution of their official responsibilities. According to the Code of Conduct for Mopani District (2017:1), a municipal staff member is required to consistently act in the municipality's best interest and in a manner that does not compromise the municipality's credibility and integrity. Good governance signifies that an organization is transparent regarding its processes and ensures that its records are accessible to shareholders, stakeholders, and other pertinent parties. This encompasses financial records, which companies must accurately report, as they could encounter legal complications in the future if records are falsified. Furthermore, reports to shareholders and stakeholders should be articulated in clear, comprehensible language, considering that not all listeners may engage with governance matters on a daily basis. Transparency fosters openness in the democratic process through reporting and feedback (Rondinelli & Shabbir Cheeman, 2003:100). Stakeholders ought to be made aware of key organizational contacts and policies and should be directed to members capable of addressing any inquiries that may arise and clarifying the reports presented. Integrity, transparency in practices, and adherence to the law are all intricately connected to corporate accountability. Jarbandhan (2021:27) asserts that transparency is a crucial component of good governance as it encourages reporting and feedback. One of the essential principles of good governance is the principle of transparency, which mandates that the public is informed of all relevant decisions and the processes that lead to those decisions.

Governance requires transparency to ensure the equitable provision of services to citizens. It establishes a balance between the formulation of policies and their enforcement in accordance with

established rules and regulations. This transparency allows citizens to freely access governmental information concerning various policies and their execution. Appropriate media channels should be developed to facilitate a clear understanding of this information. Sections 195, 215, and 217 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa 1996 stipulate that public decisions and processes must be transparent, especially to those who are directly and indirectly impacted. Individuals tasked with making governmental decisions are more inclined to perform effectively when the processes are open to scrutiny by those concerned. Many wrongful actions, such as bribery, embezzlement, and corruption, frequently occur in remote areas where public oversight is minimal (Munzhedzi, 2021:5). Van der Wal (2017:190) asserts that an ethical vision enables employees to recognize the importance of ethical standards in local governance, thereby fostering the development of an ethical culture and values within local government institutions. The Code of Conduct for Mopani District (2017:1) specifies that municipal staff members must consistently execute their official duties in good faith, with diligence, honesty, and transparency.

Professionalism

Professionalism pertains to the specific way in which individuals execute their responsibilities. It is demonstrated when an individual meets the expectations of their profession and exhibits knowledge or skills pertinent to their field. Moreover, professionalism encompasses the capacity to apply specialized problem-solving abilities, adhere to industry-specific behavioral standards, and perform tasks that are beyond the capabilities of non-professionals. Public officials are expected not only to pursue established public service objectives but also to ensure that their pursuit of these goals is aligned with ethical principles (Mafunisa, 2000:25). To embody professionalism, one must also uphold ethical standards. Training provides municipal managers and officials with the necessary skills to effectively and efficiently manage limited resources. It is the responsibility of a municipal manager to advocate for and inform the municipal council regarding the Skills Development Act, 1998 (Act 97 of 1998). This process is most effective when initiated at the highest levels and cascaded throughout the organizational hierarchy. The preceding discussion indicates that professionalism serves as a potent remedy for unethical behavior, and that education and training within local government are crucial for fostering professionalism. In the execution of public duties, such as making appointments, awarding contracts, or recommending individuals for honors and benefits, public office holders should base their decisions on merit. As stated in the code of conduct for Mopani District (2017:4) a municipal staff member is prohibited from disclosing any privileged or confidential information acquired in their capacity as a municipal employee to unauthorized individuals without proper consent.

Accountability

Accountability is a moral principle that pertains to appropriate conduct, addressing the duties of both individuals and organizations regarding their actions towards others and various agencies (Rossouw, Prozesky, Burger, DU Plessis, & Van Zyl, 2016:61). Municipal officials bear responsibility for their choices and actions to the public and must subject themselves to the necessary scrutiny associated with their roles. Moeti (2014) characterizes accountability as the duty to respond to a superior authority

concerning its authorization and allocation of resources. A manager is accountable to their superiors not only for the budget assigned but also for the ongoing decisions made regarding policy, personnel, procedures, and control issues (Munzhedzi, 2021:5). Accountability is a fundamental element of effective governance practices. While Boards occupy a high position within an organization, this does not imply that they operate without oversight or can act without restraint; instead, they are accountable to all those impacted by their decisions. This accountability extends to shareholders, stakeholders, vendors, employees, and the broader public, as their choices directly influence the company's integrity. In instances where accountability is practiced, municipal officials are responsible for the decisions they make; however, accountability cannot be enforced solely through transparency or openness.

The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, enacted in 1996, has established mechanisms that require public officials and institutions to be accountable for their actions. These mechanisms encompass parliament, the public protector, the auditor general, and judicial institutions. The auditor general is responsible for auditing the financial records of all state institutions to identify discrepancies and recommend corrective actions. Accountability serves as a fundamental principle of democracy and effective governance. This obligation compels the state, the private sector, and civil society to concentrate on outcomes and to monitor and report on their performance. The notion of accountability is an ethical principle that pertains to appropriate conduct and addresses the responsibilities of individuals and organizations towards others and various agencies (Rossouw et al., 2016:61). This concept is applied in practical contexts, particularly in outlining governance and management frameworks within public services and private entities (Oketch, 2016:2). The term is frequently used interchangeably with notions of transparency, liability, answerability, and other concepts related to the expectations of providing accounts. Municipal officials are expected to maintain a high level of openness regarding all decisions and actions they undertake. They should provide justifications for their decisions and limit the withholding of information only when it is clearly warranted by the broader public interest.

Effectiveness and Efficiency

Mafunisa (2004:290) discusses effectiveness within the realm of government as the realization of established goals and objectives, while efficiency pertains to achieving these goals with the minimal use of resources. Both effectiveness and efficiency are crucial in ensuring that institutional outcomes align with societal needs. The judicious use of societal resources to foster sustainable development is fundamental to good governance. Furthermore, it guarantees the sustainable management of natural resources, thereby safeguarding the environment. Given that state resources are finite, they must be utilized with caution and rigor. This perspective challenges the common belief that state resources are boundless and that the government has the capacity to fulfill all community demands (Thornhill, 2012:112). Municipal officials are encouraged to embody and advocate for these principles through their leadership and actions. From the aforementioned discussion, it is evident that ineffective governance leads to poor governance outcomes. Roy (2016:209) posits that good governance fosters and encourages the involvement of all societal actors in the pursuit of equity, transparency, enhanced accountability, pluralism, and a robust rule of law, all of which contribute to mitigating corruption, violence, and

poverty effectively. Board directors serve as exemplars for their organizations and should strive to embody effective practices and efficiency. If the Board encounters difficulties in making timely decisions, the organization risks losing precious time and may struggle to sustain both momentum and the necessary resources to achieve its objectives. The principles of efficiency and effectiveness in good governance highlight the government's role in managing limited resources or utilizing scarce resources for the benefit of all citizens (Jarbandhan, 2021:28). This aspect of good governance is also relevant to the environmental consequences of an organization. Good governance may involve transitions towards more energy-efficient and sustainable practices within a company.

Codes are established to safeguard the reputations of organizations. The Mopani District Municipality operates under its own code of conduct; consequently, all officials are required to comply with these regulations. As stated in the code of conduct for Mopani District (2017:1) a municipal staff member must consistently execute their office duties with good faith, diligence, honesty, and transparency. Hanekom, Rowland, and Bain (2001:163) elucidate that ethical codes are essential to guide public officials in their service to society, protect them from unfounded claims, and enhance the public perception of public service. Gilman (2005:16) notes that while standards of conduct evolve over time, examining historical standards can be beneficial in recognizing that behavioral issues often remain consistent, although technology and social contexts can significantly influence the actions deemed unacceptable.

Method

Research Design

The research utilized a mixed-methods strategy, integrating both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies to achieve a thorough understanding of the subject matter. Purposive sampling, a form of non-probability sampling, was employed to intentionally choose respondents and participants who possess expertise in ethics and service delivery within the municipality. The qualitative aspect consisted of conducting semi-structured interviews with a carefully selected group of ten (10) respondents. This group included senior municipal officials such as the Municipal Manager, the Mayor, Ward Councillors, the Local Economic Development (LED) Manager, the Integrated Development Plan (IDP) Manager, the Communication Manager, the Public Participation Manager, members of the Executive Committee (EXCO), as well as Human Resources and Finance managers, among others.

The quantitative data were examined through the use of tables, frequencies, and percentages, employing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 29.0). The foundational principles of the thematic analysis technique, which include data coding, theme identification, theme refinement, and findings reporting, are comparable to other qualitative methodologies, such as discourse analysis (Flick, 2022:169). Thematic analysis serves as a method for examining qualitative data. It entails recognizing and documenting patterns within a data set, which are subsequently interpreted for their intrinsic significance (Liebenberg et al., 2020:6; Xu & Zammit, 2020:19) these patterns can be discerned by understanding the meanings of keywords utilized by participants. The objective was to obtain comprehensive insights into the practices and perceptions associated with good governance within the municipality. For the

quantitative aspect, a structured questionnaire survey was conducted with a larger sample of 190 respondents. These participants comprised business practitioners, traditional leaders, community development workers, chairpersons of civic organizations, members of the IDP Representative Forum, and general community members. The questionnaires were crafted to gather quantifiable data regarding perceptions, experiences, and the effectiveness of governance and municipal service delivery. Ultimately, 200 respondents took part in the study, ensuring a variety of perspectives from both municipal leadership and the broader community. This triangulation of data sources bolstered the validity and reliability of the findings, facilitating a more nuanced examination of governance practices within the municipality.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1

Amendment of the Mopani District Municipality's Codes

Note. (Source: Authors' Own Illustration)

The purpose of this statement was to assess whether Mopani District Municipality had amended its existing Code of Conduct to enhance governance and service delivery. As illustrated in the chart, a significant portion of respondents, 66 (35%), agreed that the current Code of Conduct requires urgent improvement. Meanwhile, 28 respondents (15%) were unsure, 29 (15%) disagreed, and 18 (10%) strongly disagreed with the need for amendments. These results indicate that while there is notable recognition of the need for improvement, a considerable proportion of respondents either disagreed or were uncertain. Therefore, the findings suggest that there are ongoing challenges with the current Code of Conduct that must be addressed to promote better governance practices within the municipality.

Figure 2

Informing the Public about the Provisions of the Codes of Mopani District

Note. (Source: Authors' Illustration)

The study sought to determine whether Mopani District Municipality effectively informs members of the public about the Code of Conduct. According to the Figure 2, 94 respondents (50%) agreed that the municipality does provide this information, while 50 respondents (26%) strongly agreed. On the other hand, 27 respondents (14%) disagreed, and 14 respondents (7%) strongly disagreed. Only a small percentage, about 5 respondents (3%), indicated that they were unaware of any public communication regarding the Code of Conduct. These results suggest that the majority of respondents believe the municipality is making efforts to inform the public, although a notable minority still perceives gaps in communication.

Figure 3

Role of the Code of Conduct in the Fight against Unethical Conduct

Note. (Source: Authors' Illustration)

Figure 3 presents respondents' views on whether the Code of Conduct in Mopani District Municipality effectively serves its primary function in combating corruption and unethical behaviour. According to the chart, 68 respondents (36%) agreed and 32 respondents (17%) strongly agreed that the Code plays a significant role in promoting ethical conduct. However, 52 respondents (27%) disagreed, 26 (14%) strongly disagreed, and 12 respondents (6%) were unsure. These findings suggest that although a majority recognize the importance of the Code in fighting corruption, a substantial portion of respondents are either sceptical or dissatisfied with its effectiveness. Given that municipalities are service-oriented entities, it is crucial for the Code of Conduct to ensure that officials remain accountable, accessible, and committed to delivering quality service to community members without delays or neglect.

Based on the interviews conducted to explore the role of code of conduct in promoting good governance with specific reference to Mopani District Municipality, participants provided the following direct responses:

Participant A

According to the participant, the Code of Conduct should be developed ethically, promoting compliance with laws, and preventing fraud, theft, corruption, and misuse of public property. He emphasized that in South Africa's multicultural society, the Code must reflect diverse value systems and guide leaders and employees toward ethical behaviour. He concluded that the Code acts as an essential guideline for conduct and relationships, and stressed that in municipalities, it must be closely monitored to reduce corruption.

Participant B

The participant mentioned that a code of conduct ensures that managers, municipal officials and councillors in the municipality behave or conduct themselves in a good manner following policy

and procedures in place.

Participant C

This participant stated that a code of conduct helps municipal officials to know and understand what they are supposed follow in their day-to-day work and helps them to deliver the quality of service expected.

Participant D

Participant D said the code of conduct helps the employees to know what they are expected to do or how to conduct themselves when delivering basic services to the community.

Participant E

The participant stated that a code of conduct ensures that services delivered are done in a manner that builds and protects the image of the municipality.

Participant F

This participant said that a code of conduct helps municipal officials know what the municipality expects of them for the betterment of the community.

Participant G

Participant G's response was that a well-written code of conduct clarifies an organisation's mission, values and principles, linking them with standards of professional conduct, which make it easy for employees to follow.

Participant H

The participant answered that the role of the code of conduct is for the employees to follow the principles and standards that govern the municipality in order to delivery basic services to the community.

Participant I

Participant I indicated that the code of conduct guides municipal officials on the set principles, rules and policies about how employees can and cannot behave during working hours, therefore it governs the way employees conduct themselves.

Participant J

In response to the above question, the participant stated that without the code of conduct, employees can do anything they want at work, therefore, it is important for the code of conduct to be in place so that the values of the organisation define desired behaviour.

From the above information, it can be concluded that training should be aimed at enhancing ethical basic service delivery to ensure accountability for the training done or left undone. The participants agreed that the Code of Conduct is essential for guiding municipal officials' behaviour to ensure ethical and effective basic service delivery. They emphasized that the Code should reflect the municipality's mission, vision, and values, and must be ethically developed to prevent fraud, corruption, and misuse of public resources. Given South Africa's multicultural society, the Code must respect diverse value systems. Participants also stressed that regular training, preferably delivered in the employees' vernacular, is necessary to enhance understanding, promote innovation, build self-confidence, and ensure accountability among municipal staff.

Limitations and Future Studies

The study on the code of conduct for promoting good governance in Mopani District Municipality faced several limitations. Firstly, the sample size (200 respondents) may not fully represent the broader population across all wards and sectors within the district. Secondly, there was limited access to sensitive information, as some municipal

officials were reluctant to share internal governance challenges, possibly leading to partial insights. Thirdly, response bias was a concern, with some respondents potentially giving socially desirable answers on ethical issues. The time constraints of the study also meant that the research captured perceptions at a specific moment without observing long-term changes. Further research might also focus on specific aspects such as the impact of leadership ethics, public participation mechanisms, or the effectiveness of internal disciplinary structures in promoting good governance.

Recommendations

- The municipality ought to regularly organize workshops and training sessions regarding the code of conduct for all employees, councillors, and stakeholders. Emphasis should be placed on ethical leadership, accountability, transparency, and public service. A clear understanding of ethical obligations will aid in fostering a culture of duty-bound governance.
- It is essential to establish clear mechanisms for monitoring compliance with the code of conduct. Prompt and equitable disciplinary measures should be implemented against any official found guilty of misconduct. Consistent enforcement will discourage unethical behaviour and enhance public trust in municipal operations.
- The ethical conduct of municipal officials should be incorporated into their annual performance evaluations. Adherence to the code should serve as a measurable criterion, connected to promotions, bonuses, and recognition systems.
- The code should be amended to require proactive dissemination of municipal decisions, budgets, projects, and service delivery plans to the public. Feedback platforms, such as community meetings and digital portals, should be enhanced to ensure transparency and accountability.
- An independent Ethics and Integrity Unit should be established within Mopani District Municipality to oversee compliance with the Code of Conduct. This unit would manage complaints, conduct investigations, and report to both the municipal council and the community regarding adherence to ethical standards.
- In light of the evolving governance landscape, Mopani District Municipality should review and update its code of conduct every three to five years. This will guarantee that the code remains pertinent, comprehensive, and in alignment with new legal requirements, governance challenges, and community expectations.
- Senior officials, including the Mayor, Municipal Manager, and EXCO members, should consistently exemplify behaviour that aligns with the code of conduct. Ethical leadership at the highest levels will permeate through all municipal departments and shape the broader institutional culture.

Conclusion

The significance of creating mechanisms for individuals to report potential misconduct is increasingly recognized, highlighting the need for internal protocols and systems that provide adequate protection for whistleblowers associated with MDM. Codes of conduct serve as the cohesive element that binds these systems within the municipality. Without integrity, public programs cannot function effectively, efficiently, and equitably. A code of conduct offers a uniform framework that employees can utilize in every

action they undertake throughout their workday. To promote good governance, the municipal council should serve as the central authority and guardian of good governance (Masegare & Ngoepe, 2018:591). This manuscript outlines the concepts, tools, and mechanisms necessary to advance this process. Consequently, it is essential for municipalities to establish robust internal processes to ensure adherence to codes of conduct and good governance by municipal officials, as well as to address alleged violations. It is the responsibility of the municipal manager to transform unethical values into ethical standards. Thus, it can be concluded that the code of conduct for municipal officials can also function as a tool to restore the integrity of the government and tackle the socio-economic challenges currently faced by South Africa's municipalities. The findings of this study can be utilized to enhance the operational effectiveness of municipalities.

The results of this study can serve as valuable insights for the government concerning the importance of delivering services to the community, thereby reducing instances of corruption and protests within local government. It is imperative that municipal officials adhere to ethical standards and values, which are fundamental to the code of conduct, and promote good governance. To improve the efficacy of the code of conduct in fostering good governance, it is advisable for MDM to develop mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating its implementation. The code of conduct holds significant potential as a crucial instrument in advancing good governance within MDM. Nevertheless, its success relies on effective implementation, enforcement, and the dedication of all stakeholders to maintain its principles. By tackling the identified challenges and executing the suggested measures, enhanced governance outcomes can be achieved. Additional research is necessary to evaluate the influence of the code of conduct on service delivery and public confidence in MDM.

References

- Ali, M. (2015). Governance and good governance: A conceptual perspective. *Dialogue*, 10(1), 65-77.
- Bolgherini, S., & Lippi, A. (2022). Politicization without institutionalization: Relations between State and Regions in crisis governance. *Contemporary Italian Politics*, 14, 1-17.
- Cop, D. (2009). Towards a pluralist and teleological theory of normativity. *Philosophical Issues*, 19(1), 21-37.
- De Bruijn, H., & Dickie, W. (2006). Strategies for safeguarding public values in liberalized utility sectors. *Public Administration*, 84, 3.
- Disolwane, V.P.P. (2010). Enhancing ethical conduct in the South African public service. *Journal of Public Administration*, 45(3), 436-446.
- Flick, U. (2022). *The Sage handbook of qualitative research design*. Sage.
- Garrett, W. (2005). *Bad karma: Thinking twice about the social consequences of reincarnation theory*. Lanham, MD: University Press of America.
- Hanekom, S.X., Rowland, R.W., & Bain, E.G. (2001). *Key aspects of public administration*. Revised edition. International Thomson Publishing (Southern Africa) (Pty) Ltd: Oxford University Press.
- Iwuagwu, E.K. (2019). Kant's absolute good will and its implications for some current ethical issues like suicide, war and abortion. *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 07(8), 03-14.
- Jarbandhan, V. (2021). *Ethical public sector leadership and good governance: Implications for the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR)*. School of Public Management, Governance and Public Policy. University of Johannesburg viewed 03 March 2025. <<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353929900>>.
- Klimach, A., Dawidowicz, A., & Żróbek, R. (2018). The Polish land administration system supporting good governance. *Land Use Policy*, 79, 547-555.
- Kondlo, K., & Maserumule, M.H. (2010). *The Zuma administration: Critical challenges*. Cape Town: HSRC Press.
- Kwemarira, G., Ntamu, D. N., Nsereko, I., & Balunywa, W. (2023). Deontological ethical orientations and public interest in government schools. *Public Organization Review*, 23(4), 1455-1476.

- Liebenberg, L., Jamal, A., & Ikeda, J. (2020). Extending youth voices in a participatory thematic analysis approach. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 19, 1609406920934614. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406920934614>.
- MacKinnon, B. (2012). *Ethics: Theory and contemporary issues* (7th edition). United States of America: Wadsworth Cengage Learning.
- Mafunisa, M.J. (1999). Enhancing accountability and ethics in the public service: the case of the Republic of South Africa. In K. Frimpong and G. Jacques (Eds.). *Corruption, democracy and good governance* (pp. 238-247). Botswana: Lightbooks.
- Mafunisa, M.J. (2000). *Public service ethics*. Kenwyn: Juta.
- Mafunisa, M.J. (2004). Measuring efficiency and effectiveness in local government in South Africa. *Journal of Public Administration*, 39(2), 290-301.
- Mafunisa, M.J. (2007). Corruption and service delivery in the public service: The case of Limpopo Province. *Journal of Public Administration*, 42(3), 260-270.
- Maile, K. V. (2022). *Organisational ethics management to promote good governance in a national government department*. University of Johannesburg (South Africa).
- Malan, F., & Smit, B. (2001). *Ethics and leadership in business and politics*. Lansdowne: Juta & Co.
- Manyaka, R.K., & Sebola, M.P. (2013). Ethical training for effective anti-corruption systems in the South African public service. *Journal of Public Administration*, 48(1), 75-88.
- Masegare, P., & Ngoepe, M. (2018). A framework for incorporating implementation indicators of corporate governance for municipalities in South Africa. *Corporate Governance*, 18(4), 581-593.
- Matshabaphala, M.D. (2017). The ethical intelligence imperative in public administration research. *Journal of Public Administration*, 52(1), 296-304.
- Matshabaphala, M.D.J., & Ringso, J. (2022). Ethics and governance: Lessons from the past, present and the future in the public service. *Journal of Public Administration*, 57(3) September 2022.
- Mbandlwa, Z., Dorasamy, N., & Fagbadebo, O. (2020). *Ethical leadership and the challenge of service delivery in South Africa: A discourse*. TEST Engineering & Management magazine.
- Mbedzi, L. (2023). *The role of code of conduct in enhancing service delivery in local government with specific reference to Mopani District Municipality* (Doctoral dissertation), University of Venda.
- Mle T.R., & Maclean, S. (2011). *Ethics, integrity and good governance: the case of South Africa's local sphere of government*. School of Public Administration University of Fort Hare.
- Moeti, K.B. (2014). *Public finance fundamentals* (2nd edition). Cape Town: Juta.
- Mopani District Municipality (2024). *Final Code of Conduct 2025-2026*. Mopani District Municipality.
- Mopani District Municipality. Code of conduct Mopani District (2017). *Code of conduct for employees*. Pretoria: Government Printer.
- Munzhedzi, P.H., & Makwembere, S. (2019). Good governance as a solution to local economic development challenges in South African municipalities. *Journal of Public Administration*, 54(4-1), 659-676.
- Munzhedzi, P.H. (2021). Analysing the application of governance principles in the management of COVID-19 in South Africa: Lessons for the future. *Africa's Public Service Delivery and Performance Review*, 9(1), 490.
- Naidoo, G. (2011). Adopting an appropriate leadership approach to improve public service delivery in SA. *African Journal of Public Affairs*, 4.
- Ndebele, C., & Lavheleni, P.N. (2017). Local government and quality service delivery: An evaluation of municipal service delivery in a local municipality in Limpopo Province. *Journal of Public Administration*, 52, 2.
- Nyawo, J.C. (2017). Public participation and accountability in local government with particular reference to municipality. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 57(1-2), 60-69.
- Oketch, C. (2016). Ethical governance and political accountability in Bushenyi district local government. *Research Journal of Management*, 4(1), 1-10.
- Pauw, J.C., Woods, G., Van der Linden, G.J.A., Fourie, D., & Visser, C.B. (2011). *Managing public money. Systems from the South* (2nd edition). Sandown: Heinemann.
- Rangwato, T. E., Shopola, A., & Molepo, J. 2024. Analysis of the sustained poor audit outcomes in Mopani District Municipality. *Journal of Local Government Research and Innovation*, 5, 9.
- Regoli, H. (2019). *The pros and cons of deontological ethics*. <https://connectu.sfund.org/12-pros-and-cons-of-deontological-ethics>. Accessed on 26 April 2025.
- Republic of South Africa (1996). *Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996*. Pretoria: Government printer.
- Republic of South Africa (2000). *Local Government: Municipal Systems Act, 2000 (Act No. 32 of 2000)*. Pretoria: Government printer.
- Republic of South Africa (1998). *Skills Development Act, 1998 (Act No. 97 of 1998)*. Pretoria: Government printer.
- Roby, B. (2018). *Virtue Ethics, Deontology and Consequentialism*. Washington: University of Mary Eagle Scholar.
- Rondinelli, D.A., & Shabbir Cheeman, G. (2003). *Reinventing government for the twenty-first century: State capacity in a globalizing society*. United States of America: Kumarian Press, Inc.
- Rossouw, D., Prozesky, M., Burger, M., DU Plessis, C., & Van Zyl, M. (2016). *Ethics for accountants and auditors* (Revised edition). Cape Town: Oxford University Press.
- Roy, S.K. (2016). The Principle of Sustainable Development, Human Rights, and Good Governance. *Brawijaya Law Journal*, 3(2), 209.
- Singh, A. K., & Mishra, N. K. (2018). Ethical theory and business. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Development Research*, 2(1), 97-113.
- Spahn, A. (2020). Digital objects, digital subjects and digital societies: Deontology in the age of digitalization. *Information*, 11(4), 228.
- Tintswalo, S., Mazenda, A., Masiya, T., & Shava, E. (2022). Management of records at Statistics South Africa: Challenges and prospects. *Information Development*, 38(2), 286-298.
- Van der Wal, Z. (2017). *Managing ethical complexities*. The 21st Century Public Manager, 169-198.
- Xu, W., & Zammit, K. (2020). Applying thematic analysis to education: A hybrid approach to interpreting data in practitioner research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 19, 1609406920918810. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406920918810>.